

INEC and Political Parties as Determinants of Electoral Administration and Democratic Sustainability in Akwa Ibom State

Edenseting, Prince Okon

Department of Public Administration, University of Uyo

edensetingprinceokon@gmail.com

08036366228

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15794356>

Citation: Edenseting, P. O. (2025). INEC and Political Parties as Determinants of Electoral Administration and Democratic Sustainability in Akwa Ibom State. *Global Journal of Modern Research and Emerging Trends*, 1(3).

Abstract

This study investigates the critical roles played by political parties and the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) in shaping electoral administration and sustaining democratic governance in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Grounded in the Liberal Democratic Theory, the research explores how party conduct and electoral management practices influence the integrity and credibility of elections, with a focus on the 2019 and 2023 general elections. Adopting a descriptive survey design, data were gathered from 510 respondents comprising INEC officials, political party executives, security personnel, and registered voters across three senatorial districts. The findings reveal that political parties significantly affect electoral administration through voter mobilization, candidate nomination, and campaign strategies; however, their engagement is often marred by poor internal democracy, vote-buying, and electoral violence. INEC, despite introducing reforms such as the Bimodal Voter Accreditation System (BVAS), continues to face challenges related to logistics, neutrality, and institutional capacity. Chi-square analysis confirmed significant relationships between the conduct of political parties and INEC's effectiveness with electoral credibility and democratic consolidation in the state. The study recommends enhanced political party reform, improved electoral logistics, and legal safeguards to bolster INEC's autonomy and restore public trust in the democratic process.

Keywords: Political Parties, INEC, Electoral Administration, Democratic Governance, Akwa Ibom State

1. Introduction

Elections remain a fundamental instrument for establishing representative governance and ensuring political accountability in democratic societies (Diamond, 2008). In Nigeria, electoral processes have been consistently marred by irregularities, including violence, vote buying, logistical failures, and allegations of institutional compromise (Ibrahim & Ibeanu, 2009). These problems have cast doubt on the capacity of election stakeholders, particularly political parties and the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC), to contribute meaningfully to the advancement of sustainable democratic governance.

Political parties are central to democratic consolidation as they mobilize voters, select credible candidates, shape public discourse, and provide platforms for political participation (Omotola, 2010). However, in Nigeria and specifically in Akwa Ibom State, political parties have often been characterized by weak internal democracy, imposition of candidates, and electoral violence, undermining the integrity of the electoral process (Omodia, 2010). These practices distort voter choice and deepen public distrust in democratic institutions.

On the other hand, INEC as the Electoral Management Body (EMB) has been saddled with the constitutional responsibility of organizing elections, ensuring their credibility, and safeguarding the electoral process from manipulation (INEC, 2015). Despite innovations such as the introduction of the Bimodal Voter Accreditation System (BVAS) to curb electoral fraud, INEC has faced criticisms relating to logistical inefficiencies, poor staff training, and susceptibility to political interference, especially during the 2019 and 2023 general elections (Okoye, 2019). These shortcomings have raised concerns about its effectiveness in promoting sustainable democratic governance.

This study is therefore guided by two main objectives: (i) to determine how political parties affect election administration in Akwa Ibom State; and (ii) to investigate the extent to which INEC contributes to sustaining democratic governance in the state. By exploring these objectives, the research aims to provide empirical insights into the operational dynamics of these institutions and recommend measures to enhance the integrity of Nigeria's electoral processes.

1.2 Problem Statement

Sustainable democratic governance in Nigeria, particularly in Akwa Ibom State, continues to face critical challenges despite over two decades of uninterrupted democratic rule since 1999. Central to this crisis is the perceived inefficiency of election administration mechanisms, especially the role of political parties and the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) in ensuring credible, transparent, and inclusive

electoral processes. Political parties, rather than serving as platforms for mobilising voters and promoting democratic values, are often accused of encouraging electoral malpractice, political thuggery, vote-buying, and divisive campaigns that undermine public trust in the electoral process.

Similarly, INEC, despite constitutional backing and legal mandates, has frequently been criticised for operational weaknesses such as inadequate logistics, late delivery of election materials, voter disenfranchisement, and poor coordination with security agencies. These lapses contribute to electoral violence, compromised election results, and the erosion of confidence in Nigeria's democratic institutions.

Existing literature has highlighted these challenges in broad terms across Nigeria (Omotola, 2009; Inokoba & Kumokor, 2019), but there is a research gap in understanding how these dynamics specifically manifest in Akwa Ibom State—a region of political importance in Nigeria's South-South zone and one marked by history of election-related violence and political tension. This study, therefore, seeks to fill this gap by examining the direct influence of political parties and INEC on election administration and sustainable democratic governance in the state.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

- i. To determine how political parties affect Akwa Ibom State's election administration.
- ii. To examine how the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) contributes to the maintenance of sustainable democratic governance in Akwa Ibom State.

1.4 Research Questions

- i. How do political parties influence election administration in Akwa Ibom State?
- ii. In what ways does the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) contribute to the sustainability of democratic governance in Akwa Ibom State?

1.5 Hypotheses

- i. H₀₁: Political parties do not significantly influence the administration of elections in Akwa Ibom State.
H₁₁: Political parties significantly influence the administration of elections in Akwa Ibom State.
- ii. H₀₂: INEC's activities do not significantly contribute to sustainable democratic governance in Akwa Ibom State.
H₁₂: INEC's activities significantly contribute to sustainable democratic governance in Akwa Ibom State.

1.6 Significance of the Study

This study is significant as it contributes theoretically, empirically, and practically to the discourse on democratic consolidation in Nigeria, particularly within Akwa Ibom State. Theoretically, it applies the liberal democratic theory to assess the effectiveness of political parties and the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) in fostering sustainable democratic governance, thus enriching scholarly understanding of election management in developing democracies. Empirically, the study provides data-driven insights into the specific challenges confronting election administration in Akwa Ibom State, such as logistical shortcomings, political interference, and lapses in the conduct of electoral actors. Practically, its findings are expected to guide stakeholders—including INEC, political parties, security agencies, civil society organisations, and policymakers—on reforms needed to strengthen the integrity, transparency, and credibility of elections. Furthermore, by exposing areas of administrative weakness and partisan misconduct, the study raises public awareness and encourages greater civic engagement, potentially fostering a more informed electorate that demands accountability in Nigeria's electoral processes.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Political Parties and Election Administration in Nigeria

Political parties serve as vital channels through which democratic governance is realized in any state. They perform critical functions such as political education, candidate nomination, voter mobilization, and the articulation of public interests (Adele, 2013). In Nigeria, however, the functionality of political parties has been repeatedly questioned, particularly concerning their role in election administration. Scholars such as Omotola (2009) assert that political parties in Nigeria, including those in Akwa Ibom State, have often contributed to electoral malpractices through vote buying, sponsorship of thugs, and incitement of violence during elections.

In addition, the internal workings of political parties in Nigeria are frequently plagued by a lack of internal democracy, characterized by the imposition of candidates and disregard for due process (Omodia, 2010). These flaws have a cascading effect on election administration, as political parties exert undue pressure on electoral officials and undermine the credibility of the process. Political interference has also been identified as a significant factor responsible for the manipulation of electoral outcomes, which threatens democratic consolidation (Okoosi-Simbine, 2013).

2.2 INEC and Sustainable Democratic Governance in Nigeria

The Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) is constitutionally empowered to organize, undertake, and supervise all elections in Nigeria (INEC, 2015). The effectiveness of INEC in discharging these duties is fundamental to the sustenance

of democratic governance. According to Aiyede (2007), the credibility of elections conducted by INEC largely determines the public's trust in the democratic process.

Despite reforms, such as the introduction of smart card readers in 2015 and the Bimodal Voter Accreditation System (BVAS) in 2023, INEC has continued to face challenges related to logistics, human resource capacity, and susceptibility to political manipulation (Okoye, 2019). These systemic weaknesses have manifested in irregularities such as late arrival of election materials, incomplete voter registers, and non-adherence to electoral guidelines, which compromise electoral integrity and democratic consolidation.

Moreover, scholars like Ibrahim and Ibeanu (2009) argue that for Nigeria to achieve sustainable democracy, INEC must maintain neutrality, transparency, and efficiency in all electoral processes. In Akwa Ibom State, logistical inadequacies, poorly trained ad-hoc staff, and allegations of bias have significantly affected public confidence in INEC's ability to conduct credible elections.

From the reviewed literature, it is evident that political parties and INEC play pivotal but problematic roles in Nigeria's electoral process. While political parties are meant to facilitate political competition and representation, they have often exacerbated electoral tensions and violence in Akwa Ibom State. Similarly, INEC, despite notable reforms, struggles with operational inefficiencies and credibility issues.

However, few empirical studies have comprehensively explored how these two variables—political party activities and INEC's administrative performance—simultaneously impact sustainable democratic governance during the 2019 and 2023 presidential elections. This study addresses this gap by examining these relationships within the context of Akwa Ibom's unique electoral dynamics.

2.4 Theoretical Framework

This study adopts the Liberal Democratic Theory as its theoretical underpinning, given its relevance in understanding the interplay between political parties, election administration, and sustainable democratic governance.

Liberal Democratic Theory, as espoused by classical thinkers such as John Locke (1632–1704) and later expanded by modern scholars like Schumpeter (2018) and Przeworski (2020), posits that democracy thrives on principles such as political pluralism, free and fair elections, respect for the rule of law, and the protection of individual liberties. The theory asserts that the legitimacy of governance derives from the consent of the governed, which is expressed through periodic and credible elections (Ball, 2020).

A central tenet of this theory is that political parties must serve as vehicles for citizen representation, interest articulation, and political competition in a manner that promotes issue-based campaigns and ideological clarity rather than ethnicity, religion, or patronage (Kwasau, 2018). In the context of Nigeria, and specifically Akwa Ibom State, this theory underscores the expectation that political parties should contribute positively to democratic consolidation by fostering internal democracy, transparency in candidate selection, and peaceful electoral conduct.

Similarly, the theory emphasizes the critical role of electoral management bodies (EMBs) such as INEC, which are expected to provide a level playing field for all political actors. An independent and competent EMB is necessary to guarantee the credibility of the electoral process and, by extension, the legitimacy of the democratic system. This implies that INEC must demonstrate operational neutrality, administrative efficiency, and adherence to legal and ethical standards in managing elections (Ibrahim & Ibeanu, 2009).

In Akwa Ibom State, the Liberal Democratic Theory aids in analysing the extent to which political parties and INEC have either promoted or hindered sustainable democratic governance. When political parties engage in undemocratic practices—such as vote buying, thuggery, and manipulation—or when INEC fails in logistical preparations and impartiality, the foundational principles of democracy as envisaged by this theory are violated.

Therefore, the theory serves as a lens for evaluating how political party behavior and INEC's administrative capacity impact electoral integrity and democratic sustainability in the state.

3.0 Research Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This study adopted a **descriptive survey design** to investigate the influence of political parties and the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) on election administration and sustainable democratic governance in Akwa Ibom State. The survey design was suitable because it allowed for the collection of data directly from the target population regarding their perceptions, experiences, and evaluations of election administration practices and political party activities.

3.2 Population of the Study

The study population comprised the entire INEC staff in Akwa Ibom State, executive members of the two major political parties—the All Progressives Congress (APC) and the Peoples Democratic Party (PDP)—and personnel from three key security agencies involved in electoral processes: the Nigeria Police Force (NPF), Nigeria Security and

Civil Defence Corps (NSCDC), and Department of State Services (DSS). Additionally, the voting population in three strategically selected local government areas (LGA) representing each senatorial district—Mbo (Eket Senatorial District), Essien Udim (Ikot Ekpene Senatorial District), and Uruan (Uyo Senatorial District)—were included. The total population for the study was 522,722.

3.3 Sample Size and Sampling Technique

A stratified random sampling technique was employed to ensure representativeness across all groups. The sample comprised selected staff from INEC (30 respondents), security personnel (30), political party executives (25 from each party), and registered voters (400 respondents from the three LGAs). This yielded a total sample size of **510 respondents**, deemed sufficient for meaningful statistical inference.

3.4 Sources of Data

Both primary and secondary data sources were utilized. Primary data was gathered using a structured questionnaire, while secondary data came from scholarly journals, textbooks, official election reports, newspapers, government publications, and credible internet sources.

3.5 Instrumentation

The research instrument was a four-point Likert scale questionnaire containing 15 items divided into two sections based on the study objectives. Respondents indicated their level of agreement with statements using the scale: Strongly Agree (4), Agree (3), Disagree (2), and Strongly Disagree (1).

3.6 Validity of the Instrument

Content validity was ensured by subjecting the questionnaire to the scrutiny of academic experts and the research supervisor. Their corrections and suggestions were incorporated to improve the clarity, relevance, and coverage of the instrument.

3.7 Reliability of the Instrument

The reliability of the instrument was assessed using the **test-retest method**. The questionnaire was administered to 25 respondents not included in the final study population. A Pearson's correlation coefficient of **0.83** confirmed a high level of reliability.

3.8 Method of Data Analysis

Data collected were analysed using both quantitative and qualitative methods. Descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages) described the demographic characteristics and response patterns. The Chi-square (χ^2) statistical test was employed

to test the hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance to establish relationships between election administration variables (INEC operations, political party activities) and sustainable democratic governance in Akwa Ibom State. Qualitative insights from secondary sources supplemented the statistical results for a deeper interpretation of the findings.

4.1 Data Presentation and Analysis

Table 4.1: Respondents' Demographic Data

Characteristics	Frequency (N = 380)	The rate
Sex:		
Male	205	35.95
Female	175	46.05
Age (Years)		
18-22	76	20
23-27	152	40
28-32	97	25.53
33 and Above	55	14.47
Educational Qualification		
SSCE	38	10
OND./HND	134	35.26
B. Sc.	191	50.26
M. Sc. and Above	17	4.47
Respondents by LGA and Institutions		
Mbo	93	24.47
Essien Udim	96	25.26
Uruan	97	25.53
INEC	72	18.95
Police	69	18.86
NSCDC	71	18.68
DSS	72	18.95

Field Work as the source (2024).

According to the data presented in Table 4.1, 53.95% of the respondents were male, while 46.05% were female. The distribution of respondents by age shows that 20% were aged between 18 and 22 years, 40% fell within the 23 to 27 years bracket, 25.53% were aged between 28 and 32 years, and 14.47% were 33 years or older.

Regarding educational qualifications, the majority being 191 respondents (50.26%) held a B.Sc. degree, followed by 134 respondents (35.26%) with OND/HND certificates. Also, 38 respondents (10%) possessed SSCE qualifications, while 17 respondents (4.47%) had M.Sc. degrees or other advanced/professional qualifications.

The table further indicates the distribution of respondents by location and institutional affiliation: Mbo (16.32%), Essien Udim (16.84%), Uruan (17.02%), INEC staff (12.63%), Police personnel (12.02%), NSCDC officials (12.46%), and DSS operatives (12.63%).

4.2 Data Analysis

Research Question One: How do political parties influence election administration in Akwa Ibom State?

Table 4.1: The impact of political parties on election administration in Akwa Ibom State

S/N	Statements	SA	A	D	SD	Total
1.	In Akwa Ibom State, political parties	202	98	34	46	380
2.	are vital to the administration of	(53.15)	(25.78)	(8.94)	(12.10)	380
	elections.	106	112	97	65	
3.	The efficiency for the political parties		(29.4)	(25.52)	(17.10)	
4.	can help Nigeria sustain its democratic	(27.89))			380
5.	system of government.	214				
	Political parties seem unwilling to		103		40	380
	accept Nigeria's efficient election	(56.31)		23	(10.53)	380
	organization.		(27.10)	(6.05)		
	In any society, political parties are	152(40)				
	essential to the survival of democracy.		210		12	
	By securing a legitimate, open, free,	96	(55.26)	6	(3.15)	
	and equitable electoral process and	(25.26)		(1.57)		
	administration, political parties are				44	
	supposed to strengthen democracy.		214	26	(11.57)	
			(56.31)	(6.84)		

Field Work (2024) is the source.

As shown in Table 4.2, the majority of respondents acknowledged the crucial role of political parties in election administration in Akwa Ibom State, with 53.15% strongly affirming this view, 25.78% agreeing, 8.94% disagreeing, and 12.10% strongly disagreeing. On the matter of political parties contributing to the sustainability of democratic governance in Nigeria, 27.89% of respondents strongly agreed, 29.4% agreed, while 25.52% disagreed and 17.10% strongly disagreed.

Concerning the perception that political parties are reluctant to comply with electoral administration guidelines, 56.31% strongly agreed, 27.10% agreed, whereas 6.05% disagreed and 10.53% strongly disagreed. Regarding the view that political parties are fundamental to the survival of democracy, 40% strongly agreed, 55.26% agreed, with only 1.57% disagreeing and 3.15% strongly disagreeing.

Finally, on the assertion that political parties play a role in promoting democracy by ensuring free, fair, credible, and transparent elections, 25.26% strongly agreed, 56.31% agreed, while 6.84% disagreed and 11.57% strongly disagreed.

Test of Hypothesis I

H₀₁: Political parties do not significantly influence the administration of elections in Akwa Ibom State.

H₁₁: Political parties significantly influence the administration of elections in Akwa Ibom State.

Table 4.5: Observed frequencies for hypothesis 1

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD	Total
1.	Akwa Ibom State's election administration will likely to be significantly impacted by political parties.	202 (53.15)	98 (25.78)	34 (8.94)	46 (12.10)	380
2.	Sustenance of Nigeria can achieve democratic governance through its effectiveness of the political parties.	106 (27.89)	112 (29.4)	97 (25.52)	65 (17.10)	380
3.	Political parties do not want to adhere to the effectiveness of election administration in Nigeria.	214 (56.31)	103 (27.10)	23 (6.05)	40 (10.53)	380
Total		522	313	154	151	1,140

Source: Field Work (2024)

Result:

Fo = 1140
Fe = 1140.96
Calculated χ^2 = 159.31
d/f = 9
P = 0.05
Critical Value = 16.9

Decision

Table 4.4 reveals that at a 0.05 significance level, the computed Chi-square (χ^2) value of 159.31 exceeds the critical table value of 16.919. This result leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis (Ho), thereby supporting the alternative hypothesis which states that political parties significantly influence election administration in Akwa Ibom State.

Research Question Two: In what ways does the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) contribute to the sustainability of democratic governance in Akwa Ibom State?

Table 4.3: INEC's substantial contribution to Akwa Ibom State's preserving democratic governance

S/N	Statements	SA	A	D	SD	TOTAL
11.	INEC has always done their best to sustain democracy in Nigeria.	95 (25)	76 (20)	88 (23.15)	121 (31.84)	380
12.	INEC has been conducting credible election in Nigeria.	197 (51.84)	174 (45.78)	2 (0.52)	7 (1.84)	380
13.	BIVAS introduced by INEC has added of to sustainable democratic governance.	108 (28.42)	72 (18.94)	96 (25.26)	104 (27.36)	380
14.	The actions of INEC as an institution has dashed the hope of democratic governance in Nigeria.	48 (12.63)	26 (6.84)	98 (25.78)	108 (28.42)	380
15.	The present day INEC do not seems to add value to the sustainable democratic governance in Nigeria.	63 (16.57)	32 (8.42)	174 (45.78)	233 (61.31)	380

Source: Field Work (2024)

As presented in Table 4.3, 25% of respondents strongly believed that INEC has consistently contributed to sustaining democracy in Nigeria, while a larger proportion of 31.84% strongly disagreed, and 23.15% disagreed; only 20% agreed with this assertion. Regarding the claim that INEC has conducted credible elections in Nigeria, 51.84% strongly agreed, 45.78% agreed, whereas only 0.52% disagreed and 1.84% strongly disagreed.

On the introduction of BIVAS (Bimodal Voter Accreditation System) as a tool enhancing sustainable democratic governance, 28.42% strongly agreed, 18.94% agreed, while 25.26% disagreed and 28.42% strongly disagreed, indicating mixed perceptions about its effectiveness. In relation to the concern that INEC's actions have undermined public confidence in democratic governance, 12.63% strongly agreed, 6.84% agreed, with a

greater portion of respondents showing dissent as 25.78% disagreed and 28.42% strongly disagreed.

Finally, on the assertion that the current INEC has failed to contribute meaningfully to sustaining democratic governance, only 16.57% strongly agreed, 8.42% agreed, while a majority of 45.78% disagreed and 61.31% strongly disagreed, reflecting a generally favourable view of INEC's value in this regard among the respondents.

Test Hypothesis Two

- i. **H₀₂**: INEC's activities do not significantly contribute to sustainable democratic governance in Akwa Ibom State.
- ii. **H₁₂**: INEC's activities significantly contribute to sustainable democratic governance in Akwa Ibom State.

Table 4.7: Response Frequencies for Hypothesis III

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD	Total
11.	INEC has always done their best to sustain democracy in Nigeria.	95 (25)	76 (20)	88 (23.15)	121 (31.84)	380
12.	INEC has been conducting credible election in Nigeria.	197 (51.84)	174 (45.78)	2 (0.52)	7 (1.84)	380
13.	BIVAS introduced by INEC has added of to sustainable democratic governance.	108 (28.42)	72 (18.94)	96 (25.26)	104 (27.36)	380
Total		400	322	186	232	1,140

Source: Field Work (2024)

Result:

- F_o = 1140
- F_e = 759.98
- Calculated χ^2 = 293.8
- d/f = 9
- P = 0.05
- Critical Value = 16.9

Decision

Table 4.5 shows that the computed Chi-square (χ^2) value of 759.98 surpasses the critical table value of 16.919 at the 0.05 significance level. This outcome indicates that the alternative hypothesis is accepted, while the null hypothesis (H_o) which stated that INEC's activities do not significantly contribute to sustainable democratic governance in Akwa Ibom State is rejected.

Discussion of Findings

This study examined the role of political parties and the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) in the administration of elections and the promotion of sustainable democratic governance in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, with particular focus on the 2019 and 2023 general elections.

1. Political Parties and Election Administration

Findings from the analysis revealed that political parties play a significant role in shaping election administration within Akwa Ibom State. A majority of respondents affirmed that political parties are crucial actors in the electoral process, responsible for mobilizing the electorate, presenting credible candidates, and fostering issue-based political competition. However, the study also exposed challenges associated with political parties, such as poor internal democracy, imposition of candidates, and a tendency toward ethnic and personal interest politics rather than national development goals. This aligns with the observations of Yakubu (2020), who noted that political actors in Nigeria often view elections as a "do-or-die" affair, leading to electoral violence, vote-buying, and other malpractices that undermine credible election outcomes.

Furthermore, the Chi-square analysis confirmed a significant relationship between political parties and election administration effectiveness, suggesting that the performance and conduct of political parties directly influence the credibility and transparency of elections in the state. This underscores the need for political reforms to strengthen intra-party democracy and promote issue-based politics.

2. INEC and Sustainable Democratic Governance

Regarding the role of INEC, the findings indicate mixed perceptions among respondents. While some agreed that INEC has made efforts to uphold democratic principles by introducing reforms such as the Bimodal Voter Accreditation System (BVAS), others believed that the commission fell short in ensuring transparency and credibility, particularly during result collation and announcement phases. Issues such as logistical challenges, perceived bias, inadequate voter education, and compromise by INEC officials were cited as undermining factors to its effectiveness.

Despite the technological improvements introduced by INEC, such as the BVAS, a considerable proportion of respondents expressed dissatisfaction with the impact of these innovations on election credibility and democratic consolidation. This resonates with the views of Inokoba and Kukumor (2019), who argued that systemic issues such as electoral malpractices, logistical failures, and the complicity of security agencies continue to hinder free and fair elections in Nigeria.

The Chi-square test further established a significant relationship between INEC's effectiveness and the sustainability of democratic governance in Akwa Ibom State, affirming the critical role of election management bodies in shaping public trust and political stability. However, the persistent challenges identified point to the need for improved logistics, staff training, security arrangements, and enforcement of electoral laws.

Summary of Findings

This study set out to examine the influence of political parties on election administration and the role of INEC in fostering sustainable democratic governance in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Based on the analysis of data collected through surveys and statistical tests, the following key findings emerged:

i. Political Parties and Election Administration

Political parties play a central role in the administration of elections by mobilizing voters, presenting candidates, and shaping the electoral process. However, their failure to uphold internal democracy, engage in issue-based campaigns, and avoid violence undermines the credibility of the electoral process in Akwa Ibom State.

ii. INEC's Role in Sustainable Democracy

INEC has introduced reforms aimed at enhancing election credibility, such as the BVAS technology. Despite these efforts, challenges such as poor logistics, inadequate staff training, perceived bias, and weak enforcement of electoral laws persist, affecting public confidence in the commission's ability to conduct free and fair elections.

iii. Significant Relationships Identified

The Chi-square statistical analysis confirmed significant relationships between political parties and election administration, as well as between INEC's effectiveness and sustainable democratic governance, underscoring the impact of these institutions on Nigeria's electoral and democratic landscape.

Conclusion

The study concluded that both political parties and INEC are pivotal to the success of elections and the consolidation of democratic governance in Akwa Ibom State. Political parties, through their structures and operations, shape the political landscape and influence voter participation, while INEC, as the election management body, plays a critical role in ensuring electoral integrity. However, systemic weaknesses such as internal party conflicts, electoral violence, poor logistical arrangements, and perceived institutional bias continue to undermine Nigeria's democratic process. Without significant reforms in these areas, the quest for a stable and sustainable democracy in Nigeria remains uncertain.

Recommendations

In light of the findings, the following recommendations are made to strengthen election administration and promote sustainable democratic governance in Akwa Ibom State and Nigeria at large:

1. Political parties must institutionalize internal democracy, promote issue-based politics, and discourage violence and electoral malpractices. The Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) should enforce strict guidelines to regulate party primaries and candidate selection processes.
2. INEC should be provided with adequate resources, modern logistics, and continuous staff training to ensure the credibility of elections. Measures to insulate the commission from political interference must be prioritized to boost public confidence.
3. Security agencies must work collaboratively with INEC to ensure the safety of voters, electoral officers, and materials. Security planning should be integrated into election preparations early enough to address potential threats proactively.
4. Violators of electoral laws, including party officials, candidates, security personnel, and electoral staff, should be prosecuted to serve as a deterrent against future malpractices. A strict adherence to the rule of law will enhance the integrity of the electoral process.

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